

Gender Discrimination and Mental Health

Latha Paul¹ & AkshayDeepakraoMandlik²

¹Research Scholar, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangalore,
Karnataka, India

OrcidID: 0000-0003-2864-4046; E-mail: lathapaul01@gmail.com

²Research Scholar, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangalore,
Karnataka, India

OrcidID: 0000-0001-6843-0777, E-mail: akshaydm21@yahoo.co.in

ABSTRACT

In India discrimination against women has become a normal phenomenon. They have always been considered secondary citizens. We also have a very progressive constitution that talks about equality but in spite of this and many progressive legislations women are relegated to the margins and face a lot of pressure in a Patriarchal world which again directly affects their mental health.

Mental health issues are one of the main contributors to disease and disability. There are millions suffering from defined mental disorders but at the same time there are others who because of their situations can be affected by mental health issues and they include women, children, elders, people who are displaced by large development projects

In a patriarchal society such as ours where there are stereotypical thinking and also the different roles assigned to men and women and women being over burdened with productive and reproductive roles there is a lot mental pressure on women to juggle around the household chores as well as the professional roles they play as well as care givers to both their children and others in the family with very little leisure time and a lot of mental health issues many a time goes unseen and unheard.

Women are more likely than men to have anxiety depression and traumatic stress related disorders. This paper will try to explore the direct relation between mental health and gender specifically looking at the mental health of women.

Paper Type: *Conceptual*

Keywords: *Patriarchal society, Stereotypical thinking, Anxiety, Depression, traumatic stress related disorders, Constitution, Progressive legislations.*

1. INTRODUCTION:

Gender based inequality and discrimination has been one of the most demeaning experiences world over. This has been sanctioned by social, religious and cultural institutions and even constitutional sanctity, in some places. Patriarchy that authorized gender discrimination, has founded the most inhuman cruel forms of structures, traditions and practices to subjugate women for eternity. This certainly has had lasting, unfathomable impact on the psyche of women in general, notwithstanding the nationality, religion, region, language, class or profession etc.

It is found that number of women affected by mental health issues are increasing and it is far higher in number compared to men in most countries. It also appears that mental health issues in women have a direct bearing on the gender inequality and discrimination in general and the social milieu they come from, with various complex manifestation of the same, in particular.

This paper will try to look at how gender inequality and discrimination become causes for the mental health issues in women.

2. IMPLICATIONS OF GENDER DISCRIMINATION FOR MENTAL HEALTH IN WOMEN:

From the moment babies are born, their assigned sex (male or female) immediately begins to shape how they should be treated, what opportunities they should receive or how they should behave according to dominant gender stereotypes in their society. Based on their external environment, children learn very quickly that boys and girls are different – they have their own colors, toys, abilities and particular interests. These differences and assigned roles based on sex, become fundamental rationale for many ideas about what boys, girls, men and women can and cannot do. For example, most societies expect females to behave in a submissive, dependent and emotional way while males are expected to be strong, independent and stoic.

While sex difference is to do with biological characteristic, gender difference is a to do with social construct. Roles and responsibilities, obligations, right and wrongs, norms, traditions, and practices etc. have been constructed to differentiate genders. Much of it is internalized over a period of time and became the new normal. As part a patriarchal scheme aimed at subjugating women, women have been relegated to subservient roles in accordance with those norms' practices and traditions and the like. This keeps women subservient to men, permitted to perform only the subordinate roles and hold subordinate positions based on their gender identity, creating gender imbalance and discrimination in the society, according to the whims of patriarchy.

From womb to tomb women experience gender inequality and the same manifests itself in various forms. Gender based discrimination or domestic violence, sexual abuse and exploitation etc. form some of the primary causes of mental health issues among women. There are other factors like stress, socio economic inequality as well as the role of media in defaming women and assigning them to specific characters and specific roles and responsibilities.

Gender disparity and gender inequality are characterized by imbalance in power, status, health, wealth, roles and responsibilities and employment so on. This leads to deprivation of rights and freedoms and marginalization of women to the periphery, contributing to gender inequality and discrimination.

Women face various forms of social and economic impediments like access to education and employment, nominal representation in politics and other leadership positions, inequality in wages and access to productive resources. Although women are engaged in both productive and reproductive roles at the same time their hard labour is never acknowledged, recognized and compensated making them vulnerable to the whims and fancies of the menfolk, a dynamics that further leads to different kind of deprivation and consequential mental health issues.

The systematic process of perpetuating gender inequality manifests itself in various forms some which are:

- Enrollment of girl children in school is much lower. This has long term implications for the girls, when they become adults, in terms of employability.
- Wage discrimination and disparity
- Unpaid work: Women often do a lot of household chores at home like child care, elder care, household chores like cooking, cleaning, washing clothes and so on, which often go unrecognized and, in most cases, never remunerated.
-

Sexism, another expression of patriarchy, is one of the main contributors to mental health issues in women and it takes various forms such as:

- Sexist remarks
- Sexual harassment at workplace and within the family
- Gender-based violence.
- Discrimination at the work place

3. THE FEMALE BURDEN:

Right from when the girl child is born into this world and she is considered a burden to the family. In traditional families, while boys are often accorded preferential treatment, girls are deprived of resources and opportunities. This experience at home in childhood do cause deep scar on the psyche of girl children; this atmosphere of negation, rejection and 'not wanted' combined with the challenges that girl/woman faces in society do create lasting impact on her mental health.

Sexual harassment at work place is a double whammy for women. They are rendered most powerless as women are exploited of their womanhood forcefully taken. This is more pathetic as she is not able to speak about as she is further victimized once it comes to the public domain. This leads to woman then silently bottling up her scars, fears and emotions which one day would explode into a mental health calamity.

There is a close connection between gender discrimination and inequality and various forms of mental health issues that women undergo such as anxiety disorders, panic disorders, depression, eating disorders, PTSD, suicidal tendencies etc. In the case of women who feel empowered and who venture to break these shackles of enslavement and discrimination meet with alienation and marginalization; they very often become victims of various form of violence including domestic violence; they are stigmatized and excluded from the society. This complex state of affairs is certainly detrimental to mental health wellbeing of women.

Gender discrimination leads to various types of psychiatric disorders like depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, depressive anxiety and somatic symptoms. These forms of mental health issues aggravate when the discrimination is more personal and obvious. Denial of rightful share in parental property, wage discrimination, denial of promotions in job etc., could trigger episodes of depression or anxiety or other disorders.

4. MENTAL HEALTH ISSUES AMONG WOMEN – A FACT SHEET:

Severe life events that inflict a sense of loss, inferiority, humiliation or entrapment do lead to depression and other mental health issues. Depression, anxiety, psychological distress, sexual violence, domestic violence and escalating rates of substance use affect women to a greater extent than men across different countries and different settings. Stress created by their multiple roles, discrimination and associated factors of poverty, hunger, malnutrition, overwork, domestic violence and sexual abuse, accounts for poor mental health in women. There is a clear relationship between the severity of such social factors and the severity of mental health problems in women. The following would offer a perspective into the status of women's mental health in comparison with the men.

- Depressive disorders account for close to 41.9% of the disability from neuropsychiatric disorders among women compared to 29.3% among men.
- Leading mental health problems of the older adults are depression, organic brain syndromes and dementias and a majority are women.
- An estimated 80% of 50 million people affected by violent conflicts, civil wars, disasters, and displacement are women and children.
- Lifetime prevalence rate of violence against women ranges from 16% to 50%.
- At least one in five women suffer rape or attempted rape in their lifetime.

5. DETERMINANTS OF MENTAL HEALTH:

If freedom, including freedom from fear and wants; dignity, social acceptance, ownership and access to resources are key determinants of mental health conversely marginalization, exclusion, discrimination, deprivation, inequality, enslavement and exploitation could be understood as some of the key determinants of mental ill-health.

6. DETERMINANTS OF MENTAL ILL HEALTH:

Although there are determinants of mental ill health in general, in the case of women patriarchy provides the overarching milieu that defines the life of women and thus forms the fundamental cause of mental health issues. In patriarchal social order men hold the absolute power and women have no say. Patriarchy, with its all-powerful systems structures and tools to controls and subjugate women and take away their rights freedom and dignity is the bedrock of the socio cultural and religious context and that becomes the principal cause of mental health issues in women.

Patriarchy can be understood as the fundamental imbalance in the society, which is tilted towards men. This imbalance is in force with regard to every aspect of life. In a patriarchal society, women have identity of their own, they their opinions have no value. Women are trained to be silent, even in the face of most horrific situations; so, they tolerate abuse exploitation, denials in silence. Patriarchy curbs their freedom to think, let alone make decisions. From the name they take, the clothes they wear, to their daily activities, patriarchy decides.

Modern day patriarchy manifests subtly like a name, a stereotype or a phrase and the like and it could be harsh like abuse, suppression or violence.

In essence patriarchy discriminate women, controls women, appropriate all that rightfully belong to women; and as result they are perpetually under enslavement, exclusion, denial, deprivation and dehumanization. Patriarchy is the prime obstacle to women's advancement and development. Patriarchal institutions and structures are responsible for the secondary status of women. Most of the mental health problems among women stem from the patriarchal system.

6.1 Determinants of Mental ill Health:

In general, mental ill health germinates from enslavement, oppression, discrimination, exclusion, dehumanization and deprivation and the like. This in general applicable to both men and women alike.

6.2 Determinants of Mental Ill Health in Women:

Although in general determinants of mental health remain more or less same for both men and the women alike, in the case of women, patriarchy and its paraphernalia create much more traumatic environment that becomes the breeding ground for all and every mental health issue of women.

The following are some of such determinants that create impediments to psychosomatic wellbeing of women.

(A) Historical Patriarchal Tools: Norms, structures, systems, traditions and practices established to further the objectives of patriarchy that excluded women and denied and deprived them of their rights and privileges and robbed them of their identity. Centuries of systematically established socio-religious and cultural structures and systems founded on the precepts of patriarchy took away women their freedom, dignity, access to resources, right to be part of decision-making process, right to political participation, religious freedom, social and cultural inclusion and relegated women to a sub-human status of least importance. Women have been kept, for centuries, a commodity, and an object for man's enjoyment.

The women psyche developed and or maimed, has happened as a direct consequence of the patriarchal adventures on the person of women, both body and spirit. This has actually created a subservient, dehumanized and enslaved, community of 'objects' for man's use.

The platter of psychosomatic problem in majority of women in society is the result of the shattered psyche, a necessary consequence of patriarchal distortion of society, visible in some of the following:

1. Normated Gender Roles: Patriarchy induced subservient gender roles have been the norm for the women to strictly follow. Some the following have a clear relation with regard to the control that men exerted on women

through these gender roles and the mental health issues that they land in subsequently.

- (a) Household responsibilities: When it comes to household responsibilities most of the burden of child care and the household chores of cooking, cleaning washing, upkeep of the home and the like fall upon the woman. Women have very little leisure time and spend long hours on household chores as well as going out to work. This leads to a lot of stress among women.
- (b) Elder Care: Elder care, very often falls upon women. This could very often be physically and emotionally draining experience

Studies show that caregivers have a higher incidence of depression due to various reasons associated with care giving such as getting less sleep and exercise, having less leisure time, not able to socialize with friends and family, unpaid work at home leading to her being more dependent on the male counterpart all of this leading to a strain on her mentally and physically.

2. Denial of Access to Resources and family properties

Gender is the main determining factor in a patriarchal society with regard to access, power and control of over the economic resources. Denial and deprivation of access to productive resources and family assets to women have been an effective tool of patriarchal control over women, thus rendering women a vulnerable lot, a certain condition that adds to the fears, anxieties and depression.

3. Power and Decision Making – A Male Monopoly: Men, in patriarchal societies have appropriated almost complete share in power. Women in general have no say at home nor do they have say in matters concerning society. Men exercise this power to have further control over women. Political participation was denied to them for a long time until recently when space and opportunities were created to accommodate women in democratic political process. Sadly, even till this day, the political role and participation on women remain largely nominal and even the few who are in positions of power are just a puppet in the hands of their patriarchal lords. Vulnerability that comes with powerlessness is a condition that helps the build-up of mental issues and challenges into a full-blown mental catastrophe.

4. Wage discrimination and work place ethos:

Work and earning are parameters of economic mobility and independency. Women securing both upward movement and economic freedom are seen as antagonistic to the patriarchal system. Women therefore face enormous gender discrimination at workplace as wage disparity, bias in hiring and promotions and the like leading to anxiety and depression among women.

Blatant discrimination that puts women at a disadvantage, such as wage disparity for the same kind of work, sexual harassment at workplace, denial of promotion to women, work atmosphere insensitive to women place a lot of pressure on women. Workplace discrimination takes various forms affecting women and other gender identities the most. Women's work is often undervalued. Much of what is spoken against such experiences are brushed aside and hushed up. Women who are discriminated against at work, especially when they are considered as lesser humans than their colleagues, certainly contribute to poor mental health.

5. Denial of Religious, cultural space – temple entry, religious roles etc.,

Religion plays a pivotal role in the lives of people. It is indeed the most powerful institution, so to say. Most religions, but, entertain a notion of uncleanness - unholiness associated with women. As a result, women are kept away from the religious roles and responsibilities and even from places of worship, thereby keeping them away from the symbolic power center of the society. This deliberate act of denial of participation in religious matters is both an assertion of male superiority and a reinforcement of female vulnerability. Bottling this inhuman treatment would have volcanic effect, impacting the emotional health of the hoarder.

(B) Modern Expressions of Patriarchy: Male aggression to reinforce patriarchal agenda is visible in the modern

expressions of patriarchy. In many cases, modern form of patriarchal expressions are a response to the assertion of women power and economic freedom that they have attained, patriarchal warlords attempting to recapture the losing ground. It often are violent actions of various kinds ranging from sexual abuse, marital abuse, wage discrimination, exclusion from postings and promotions, physical atrocities such as mutilations, to exclusion from political process, exclusion from education and opportunities and the like. Needless to say, these are traumatic experiences capable of causing imbalance to the psyche of a person.

(a)Traumatic Incidents and Mental health:

There can be many traumatic incidents in a women's life like child abuse, sexual assault, being discriminated from childhood based on their gender, various discriminatory practices like FGM's and the like.

Trauma is one of the psychological effects of sexism. It is a reaction to experiencing a severely distressing events that can cause a wide range of mental and physical disturbances like anxiety and panic attacks, anger, sadness, numbness, insomnia or nightmares, dissociation, or feeling disconnected from one's own thoughts, feelings, or body, hyperarousal, which puts the body into a state of alertness, making it difficult to relax, flashbacks and so on. Traumatic events can affect people differently. If the symptoms persist for long periods after a traumatic event, people may progress to PTSD.

Women are also more likely to experience childhood neglect, intimate partner abuse, the sudden loss of a loved one, and inhuman practices of female genital mutilation (FGM), which according to the World Health Organization (WHO) there are estimated 3 million cases of girls undergoing FGM every year, most of whom are under the age of 15 years old. These experiences, no doubt, are traumatic ones for any age group of women.

Traumatic events and depression and anxiety:

Women are subjected to domestic violence, sexual harassment and various forms of emotional psychological abuses. Victimization could occur when they are children adolescents or even later age. Women are subjected to physical, sexual, financial or emotional abuse basically as a power game for men to control women. Forced marriages, honor killings and trafficking etc. are also traumatic experience for women

All these forms of discrimination and violence faced by the girl child can be associated with a lot of mental illness that develop later in their lives. Childhood maltreatment is significantly associated with physical and mental illnesses, such as cardiovascular disease and mood disorders in adulthood; these associations have been shown to be strongest in women. The experience of domestic violence and abuse can lead to the development of mental health problems. For instance, a recent meta-analysis reported a seven-times increase in the likelihood of PTSD among women exposed to domestic violence and abuse. Childhood maltreatment is also a risk factor for domestic violence and abuse. In fact, victimization in childhood and adulthood has been shown to have a cumulative impact on mental health of women. Specifically, women with a history of childhood maltreatment, and who are exposed to domestic violence and abuse, have the highest risk of depression followed by those who have experienced only one of these victimization types; women with no such victimization histories show the lowest risk of depression. Studies converge to show that childhood maltreatment and domestic violence and abuse have grave impact on women's mental health.

(b) Sexual harassment

Sexual harassment happens from a very young age and girls who are sexually abused most often by the immediate family members an uncle or a distant relative and very often carry these scars into their adulthood as very often they cannot speak about this as it has happened within the family and they are afraid to speak the truth.

It is found that during their lifetime, 81% of women and 43% of men reported at least one incident. Women with disabilities were the most likely to experience physically aggressive harassment and assault. For most people, the age they first experienced harassment was between 14–17 years old.

Both the experience of harassment and the fear of experiencing harassment have a damaging effect on mental health. Sexual harassment could in turn lead to PTSD, lower quality sleep and the like.

(c) A lot of mental health issues sprout from the following

Lower self-esteem: A cross cultural study found that across 48 nations men had higher self-esteem on an average than women. The reasons for this were mainly the gender roles, stereotypes and the pressure on women to always fit in to certain beauty standards.

Low self-esteem also can set in at a very early age especially in our context where a male child is always preferred than a female child and it also continues through early education and childhood where boys are always given more opportunities in the field of higher education and sports etc., as boys are considered an asset whereas a girls will be married of and will become an asset to some other family.

Body image and eating disorders

Women have the pressure to fit in to the ideal body image as portrayed by the media, in accordance with the patriarchal narration and this leads to a lot of mental health issues. Self-esteem can be closely related to body image, or how a person feels about their physical appearance. A 2019 report from the British charity Mental Health Foundation found that when it came to body image:

- 25% of women and 15% of men felt shame
- 40% of women and 28% of men felt anxious
- 45% of women and 25% of men felt depressed

This low self-esteem and body image lead to various mental issues including eating disorders among women. Women in order to lose weight do a lot of diet plans leading to anorexia and other forms of eating disorders affecting physical and mental wellbeing.

7. CONCLUSION:

Both men and women face mental health issues in most societies. Men and women are in a way victims of a demanding and complex context of socio economic and politico religious dynamics. Mental health problems that emanate from this chaotic context do create more and more people with mental health challenges. However, the patent difference in the case of women is that apart from the demanding chaotic context, the patriarchal forces add fuel in the fire and has made life miserable for women. Thus, women's mental health issue is the consequence of both the demanding context and the premeditated scheme of patriarchal subjugation.

Centuries of patriarchal systems, processes, structures and tools of oppression exclusion and dehumanization has created a collection of 'female objects' without a mind of their own or one with a shattered psyche; affecting the emotional and mental wellbeing in one half of the population. Present state of mental health issues in women is a direct consequence of these processes that took away the mind and persona of women. Present status on mental health problems among women in India and elsewhere in the world points to the fact that patriarchal scheme for subjugating women, with all its structures, tools and paraphernalia has become the fundamental cause of mental ill health in women.

These discriminatory practices have created an atmosphere of patriarchal hegemony that denied and deprived women of their rights to health, education, employment and so on, which in turns pull them down to the lower rung of socio-economic ladder, a necessary environment to nurture mental ill-health. Negative experiences of subjugation, denials and deprivations have had grave effects on their mental health and well-being.

Notwithstanding the education, social reforms and constitutional democratic progress world over and efforts to address the issues with regards to the rights and status of women in society have largely remained tokenism. Efforts to look into the mental health issue of women, therefore, have to necessarily consider the fundamental causes of the mental health issues in women. Structural changes that are needed to ensure equal treatment of women in every sphere of life like social economic cultural religious and political realms are prerequisite of a genuine serious effort to restore rights freedoms status of women and along with-it mental health and well-being.

Greater efforts are needed to reduce gender discrimination in society; raising awareness, effective implementation of existing policies, more equal representation of women in positions of power, as well as creating environment that promote gender equality is nothing but an imperative.

As they say ‘put your house in order first’. Home is where our children are initiated into accepting gender norms, values and stereotypes. Children are taught their first lessons on gender roles and biases by the parents. It is parents who teach boys and girls about different behaviors and activities based on their gender. (Leaper,2014)

The most damaging impact of restrictive gender norms is that they hurt everyone. People are expected to conform to rigid ideas which limit the spaces and the behaviors in accordance with acceptable gender norm for their assigned sex. It is the same gender norms that directly or indirectly result in girls and women experiencing violence and harassment. In addition, the issue of body image where large percentage of women becoming too conscious about their physical form, is a result of gender norms and stereotypes imposed on women. These widespread ideas about what it means to be a woman, girl, man or boy can be deal with at home where parents could help their girl children identify and confront imposed dominant gender norms.

7.1 Confronting Gender Stereotypes and Roles:

The entire responsibility about how their children perceive gender cannot be placed on homes and parents. The external world that includes peers, teachers, caretakers and the media have great impact on how children think about themselves, their gender roles and behaviors as per their assigned gender. Therefore confronting gender roles and stereo types should necessarily begin with this core pressure group.

7.2 Challenging the Prevalent Gendered attitudes:

Gender inequality continues to grant men and boys with more rights, privileges and opportunities to become key decision makers and influencers. Girls and women, however, are denied opportunities to develop themselves and improve their social conditions – simply because they are female. (“Why Gender Inequality Often Starts at Home.”) And in many developing countries, girls and women are not free to exercise basic human rights like education, health and protection – this further perpetuates serious global issues such as intergenerational cycles of poverty, child early and forced marriage, gender-based violence and high maternal and new born mortality rates. (“Why Gender Inequality Often Starts at Home.”)

When men work towards equal partnership at home it is closely related to how it brings about gender equality at work. (Smith and Johnson, “Gender Equity starts at Home.”)

This study shows that women with equal partners at home are more successful at work. When people are less concerned with the impact of their job on family responsibilities and able to focus and commit more fully to their work, it’s no surprise that they’re more productive and able to take advantage of growth and advancement opportunities.

Secondly, fathers who are equal domestic partners role model equity for their children, shaping expectations of our future workforce. Daughters with dads who do their fair share are more likely to pursue their career aspirations, often in less stereotypical occupations, with more self-esteem and self-autonomy. Sons who see their father role model equal partnership in household duties have a more egalitarian perspective of women’s and men’s roles at

home and work.

Finally, men who equally share unpaid work at home aren't afraid to ask for and talk about why they need flexibility in their work schedule. When women alone request and use flexible work arrangements, paid sick leave, and parental leave, the perception that these programs exist solely for women creates a stigma that deters men from using them. For example, although men are more likely to be in jobs that allow telework, women still telework more than men. But when men lean in to truly equal partnership at home, they tend to use flexible work policies, normalizing it for everyone.

7.3 Leverage your partnership at home

If we believe gender equity begins at home, we can make home the environment where we treat our boys and girls equally and can where men and women can share in the roles and responsibilities of child rearing and caring equally, where men can support their partners careers and also allow women an equal share in the decision making and all other aspects that would make the home a conducive atmosphere where gender equality prevails and women's mental health is taken care of.

8. ANSWER TO THE PROBLEM LIES IN THE PROBLEM ITSELF:

To resolve the enormous problem of known and suppressed mental health issues of women, what is required is a holistic approach which includes:

- a) Reform Religion and Culture: If Religion culture and social structures have been dehumanizing, then the solution lies in reforming and reinventing religion culture and social structures and that they be made accountable vis-à-vis equal treatment of men and women with the help of legal constitutional institutions and instruments.
- b) A legal framework that would seriously and genuinely address the root of the problem – Property rights, protection from domestic violence, political participation, equal right to education, parity in wage, employment and promotions and so on and so forth.
- c) Accord presently toothless tigriss National / State Women Commissions, Independent Judicial Status, with judicial powers and infrastructure and funds to effectively monitor and bring into justice those who violate rights of women.
- d) National and State level Mechanisms to be established to offer Holistic Care to women: Such an establishment would identify and offer mental health care, trauma care, and offer support service such as transit homes, wholistic mental health rehabs and the like.
- e) Reform and develop a modern understanding Social Cultural and Religious structures, practices and traditions and propagate them in the society. Make these social institutions accountable to ensuring equality and respect to women through necessary legislation and their effective implementation.
- f) Establish National State mechanisms and schemes for economic and political inclusion of women
- g) Institute effective legislations to protect the rights and freedoms of women: One of the reasons for the pathetic state of affairs with regard to women and their mental health quotient is the failure of the pro-women protective legislations. Whatever legislations we have, have remained nominal, symbolic ones with neither a will nor required supportive mechanism to implement. Therefore, rewriting the legislation and establishing necessary mechanism and budget for their effective implementation is nothing but a necessity.

REFERENCES:

[1] Smith, David G., and W. Brad Johnson. “Gender Equity Starts in the Home.” *Harvard Business Review*, May 4, 2020. <https://hbr.org/2020/05/gender-equity-starts-in-the-home>.

[2] Plan International Canada. “Why Gender Inequality Often Starts at Home,” November 10, 2017. <https://stories.plancanada.ca/why-gender-inequality-starts-at-home/>.

[3] Plan International. “Gender Inequality and Early Childhood Development.” Accessed December 1, 2021. <https://plan-international.org/publication/2017-06-08-gender-inequality-and-early-childhood-development>.

[4]<http://www.learnwhr.org/wp-content/uploads/D-Facio-What-is-Patriarchy.pdf>

[5] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/social-sciences/patriarchy>

[6] Medical News Today Newsletter Medically reviewed by N. SimayGökbayrak, PhD—Written by Jayne Leonardon June 30, 2021

[7] WHO-August 2021 Mental health Newsletter